

TUDOdata: Bridging Institutional Standards and International Visibility in Research Data Management

Implementing Structured Curation Processes to Enhance Research Data Quality and Global Accessibility

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Abstract

Research data is a valuable resource that forms the foundation for scientific progress across disciplines. According to the guidelines of the German Research Foundation (DFG) on good scientific practice¹, universities must store research data in a usable form for at least 10 years. To support researchers in this task, TU Dortmund University provides TUDOdata, a trustworthy repository for managing and publishing research data. However, offering a repository alone does not address the complexity of ensuring high-quality and reusable data. To meet these challenges, TU Dortmund University has established a structured curation process aligned with its principles of research data management² and the FAIR³ principles.

TUDOdata serves researchers across diverse disciplines, from natural sciences to social sciences, providing tailored support for their unique data management needs. The platform also aligns with the goals of the National Research Data Infrastructure (NFDI), distributing research data for broad reuse. Its underlying technology Dataverse⁴ supports subrepositories, referred to as collections, which can incorporate customized metadata schemes designed to meet specific disciplinary requirements. This flexibility allows TUDOdata to implement guiding principles developed by NFDI⁵ consortia alongside discipline-specific standards while reinforcing global efforts toward open data and interdisciplinary collaboration.

Beginning their work with TUDOdata, researchers must contact the Research Data Service at TU Dortmund University⁶ to ensure compliance with institutional standards and receive tailored guidance on preparation steps. This process establishes dedicated collections where working groups can organize their data within each faculty's hierarchy, reflecting TU Dortmund University's organizational structure. Researchers

are informed about system usage and conditions while receiving advice on dataset preparation regarding format selection, metadata provision, readme files, and licensing options⁷. Templates are provided for creating detailed readme files and license documents⁸.

Prior to publication, submitted datasets undergo review by a data curator who evaluates files and metadata with respect to formal criteria and offers recommendations for improvement. Once finalized, publication rights are granted so that datasets receive their reserved DOIs (Digital Object Identifiers) and become publicly accessible. By guiding researchers through metadata preparation and licensing choices, TUDOdata addresses common barriers to publishing reusable research data while enhancing discoverability through standard APIs that facilitate integration with third-party tools.

With its established curation process, TUDOdata improves both the quality of published research data and international visibility of TU Dortmund University's outputs. As more datasets are published via TUDOdata, deeper insights into disciplinary requirements emerge – insights that inform alignment with NFDI consortia's guiding principles while ensuring visibility within NFDI frameworks. These efforts pave the way for broader interdisciplinary collaboration and innovation in global research data sharing. In the future, we aim to integrate advanced tools for automated metadata generation into TUDOdata, provide long term availability and enhanced interoperability with other NFDI repositories, further strengthening its role as an essential infrastructure component in modern scientific workflows.

Keywords: institutional repository, interdisciplinary collaboration, RDM

Resources

Overview of the publication process

Author contributions

Conceptualization, Visualization, and Methodology: Bernd T. Zey, Patrick J. Kibies and Lars E. Schumann

Validation: Julia Stapels, Wibke Kleina and Olaf Kletke

Project administration, Supervision, and Writing – original draft: Olaf Kletke

Writing – review & editing: all

Competing interests

The authors declare that they have no competing interests.

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References

- [1] German Research Foundation (DFG). (2019). *Guidelines for Safeguarding Good Scientific Practice*. Retrieved from <https://zenodo.org/records/14281892>
- [2] Principles of research data management at TU Dortmund University (2019) <https://www.tu-dortmund.de/en/research/research-data-management/principles-of-rdm/>
- [3] Wilkinson, M., Dumontier, M., Aalbersberg, I., et al. (2016). *The FAIR Guiding Principles for scientific data management and stewardship*. *Scientific Data*, 3(160018). DOI: [10.1038/sdata.2016.18](https://doi.org/10.1038/sdata.2016.18)
- [4] Dataverse Project. (n.d.). *Dataverse Documentation*. Retrieved from <https://dataverse.org>
- [5] Status quo und Zukunft der NFDI - Eine Perspektive der Fachkonsortien (2025) <https://zenodo.org/records/14726487>
- [6] TU Dortmund University Research Data Service. *Information on Research Data Management and TUDOdata Repository*. Official website: <https://fdm.tu-dortmund.de/en/>
- [7] Zey, Bernd Thomas, 2024, "Wie publiziere ich meine Daten in TUDOdata? / How do I publish my data in TUDOdata?", <https://doi.org/10.17877/TUDODATA-2024-LYPSTGCJ>, TUDOdata, V2
- [8] Zey, Bernd Thomas, 2024, "Vorlage für Readme-Datei / Template for Readme file", <https://doi.org/10.17877/TUDODATA-2024-LY45NXA8>, TUDOdata, V1